

Performing Artistic Interventions for the Promotion of Underprivileged Children in Rural Schools in Zimbabwe through Provision and Training of Mbira

Forward Mazuruse

Abstract. This paper is an update of the applied activities that have so far been undertaken by the researcher in his ongoing project, the focus of which is on promoting children who have no access to traditional music instruments. This applied study was prompted by the fact that mbira, as one of the masterpieces of Zimbabwe, is less taught and known to children in the majority rural schools. The study identified a school in Chegutu East and two in Zaka East as the first to benefit. These schools were selected randomly. In each case, the researcher donates mbira (nyunganyunga) and conducts a workshop in which two mbira pieces are taught. So far, the researcher has visited the first school, Bright Star Academy in Chegutu, located 155 kilometers from Harare the capital city of Zimbabwe on the 4th of December 2019. During the workshop, the researcher conducted elementary mbira lessons with children and eventually donated two mbiras which were left with the school for further training sessions. The workshop was attended by teachers and parents too. The researcher had an opportunity to explain the vision of the project to parents, teachers, and children. The outcomes of the workshop were that children were very excited, and quick to master the skills of not only playing the instrument but also singing along. The piece learned was Chemutengure which is one of the folk songs of Zimbabwe. The next school to be visited will be Machiva and Dabwa in Zaka. The mbira sets to be donated have already been acquired. The handover has been stalled by the pandemic, which has seen schools close in Zimbabwe. The website www.unesco.org carries McLaren's (2001) article "Case Study: Teaching Dance to Children in Zimbabwe: The Chipawo Experience," in which he writes "if one examines the education system, the media and Zimbabwean society as a whole, it is obvious that there is virtually no scope for children to express themselves or make their feelings and thoughts felt. At a time when children are particularly vulnerable and subject to many abuses, this is a serious disability. Through arts education and development, both on stage and through the media, children are empowered to make their voices heard." The above quote implies that by donating mbira we are empowering children to make their voices heard and giving them an instrument to fight abuse.

In his 2014 book *Music Rocking Zimbabwe* Zindi writes "The function role of music in the traditional culture has created a direct relationship between the preservation of the music and the preservation of culture." He further alludes that on individual basis and outside ceremonial contexts, the mbira is used by the player for meditation or deepening one's contemplation, imagination, and depth of thought. Zindi's writing implies that donating mbira to kids is an act of preservation of Zimbabwean culture as well as the music. A song like Chemutengure was coined over a century ago and having kids learn it on the mbira is assuring continuity of Zimbabwean folk music. The big lesson is that music is a good tool for cultural preservation Giving kids the mbira also empowers them with a meditation tool that enhances their imagination.

Forward Mazuruse is a prolific composer, guitarist and a music producer born 39 years ago in Zaka district of Masvingo province. His passion for music started as early as 5 in the

remote area of Zaka where he was born. He would produce sound from makeshift musical instruments. Amid so many challenges in establishing himself musically, he has carved his name among the best instrumentalists in Zimbabwe. In 2008 Mazuruse established Revival Studios, which has become home to many artists and has produced over 300 albums. Forward's passion for developing underprivileged children has given rise to the registered trust called Music for Development Foundation, through which he empowers underprivileged children by giving them access to the studio and offering training in musical instruments and vocals. His passion is driven by the fact that he shares the same history with the kids of lack of access to musical instruments. Currently he is studying for an honors degree in Music Business, Musicology and Technology with Midlands State University in Zimbabwe. Forward's dream is to help underprivileged children by establishing arts centers in their communities. This will see them access musical instruments and studio facilities without traveling to cities as is the norm in Zimbabwe. Land for the first Centre has been availed by a local council in Zaka, 350 kilometers from the capital city. He wants to use his story to inspire underprivileged kids to see possibilities that are there in perusing their musical talent.

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